

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF FRUITS AND VEGETABLES SORTING MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

In everyday applications, sorting and packaging fruits and vegetables typically requires significant manual labor. Our challenge is to reduce this manpower and enhance productivity by developing an automated sorting mechanism. The proposed system begins with loading the produce into a hopper. An IR sensor detects the passing items and sends signals to an Arduino board. A color sensor identifies the color of the produce, while a gas sensor detects any damage. Based on these inputs, the Arduino board controls a servo motor to sort the items according to their size. This sorting process operates without electricity, making it especially suitable for rural areas where it can handle large volumes of fruits and vegetables efficiently.

Key words: - Sorting, mitten and color sensor, Agriculture industry.

1. Introduction

Automatic classification is crucial in marketing to enhance speed and reduce misclassification. Fruits, being valuable export products, require precise grading, which traditionally involves labor-intensive manual work. To accelerate the process and minimize human error, an automated grading system is essential. This system uses color and ripeness to sort fruits efficiently. It detects the ripeness of each fruit, sends signals to a stepper motor and actuators, and sorts the fruit based on size. Unlike existing machines, which lack sorting capabilities for various types of fruits and vegetables, this new system can classify different fruits by their shape and size. It operates manually, requiring no electricity or additional power sources for size sorting.

2.Literature

M.M. Sofa et al [1]: Design of An Automatic Apple Sorting System Using Machine Vision This study proposes an automatic apple sorting and quality inspection system, which is based on real-time processing. Golden and Starching Delicious, and Granny Smith apple cultivars are sorted into different classes by their colour, size, and weight. It also detects apples affected by scab, stain, and rot. The proposed system consists of a roller, transporter and class conveyors combined with an enclosed cabin with machine vision, load cell and control panel units. The roller and transporter conveyors have two channels. To analyse the visual properties of apples, two identical industrial colour cameras are set on the roller conveyor. Four images of any apple rolling on the conveyor can be captured and processed using image processing software in 0.52 s. As a result, the proposed machine can sort on average 15 apples per second using two channels, in real time.

Shivleela R Arlimatti [2]: Window Based Method for Automatic Classification of Apple Fruit This paper introduces a class machine of one kind of apple fruit with nearest neighbor classifier the machine encompasses preprocessing, dividing the photo into windows, functions collection, window removal and class or decision-making step. It discriminates stem cease / calyx from defected pores and skin which can be herbal components of the apple fruit. Statistical functions are extracted from every window after which the fruit is classed through a supervised nearest neighbor classifier.

Niraj Koli et al [3]: Design and Development of Fruit Sorting Machine and summary guide fruit sorting device through length might be a tool designed to kind culmination of various sizes through keeping apart them into awesome organizations primarily based totally on their dimensions. This form of device might be manually operated, without the usage of power or every other shape of strength and might be appropriate for small-scale fruit sorting operations. The device might include a platform or desk with distinct-sized slots in it, organized in a selected pattern. The fruit might be located on pinnacle of the platform, after which slide through till they fall through the gaps into distinct booths or packing containers below, taken care of through their length. The layout of the device might rely upon the form of fruit being taken care of as distinct culmination have distinct shapes, sizes, and weights. The operator might want to regulate the scale and association of the slots in step with the fruit being taken care of. The major benefit of a summary guide fruit sorting device through length is that it could be operated without the want for power or every other shape of strength, making it best to be used in rural regions or in conditions in which strength isn't without difficulty available. However, it could now no longer be appropriate for sorting massive volumes of fruit, as it might require good sized guide labour and time.

Mathew George [4]: Multiple Fruit and Vegetable Sorting System Using Machine Vision Multiple Fruit and Vegetable Fruit Sorting System the use of Machine Vision is presented. The grading structures had been advanced to ease the labour-extensive paintings and create consistency withinside the excellence of the product. The modern grading structures worried in fruit sorting cater to simplest one sort of fruit. So, through including greater functions like fruit and vegetable identity below variable historical past situations we will beautify the excellent of the rural produce. This paper proposes a way to reap more than one fruit and vegetable sorting the use of fuzzy good judgment and K means clustering approach using a low-fee photo shooting device.

Razieh Pourdarbani et al [5]: Study on An Automatic Sorting System for Date Fruits In the prevailing study, a gadget imaginative and prescient primarily based totally, online sorting gadget become developed, the goal being to type Date result (Berthe CV.) primarily based totally at exceptional ranges of adulthood, specifically Khalaf, Rotan and Tamar to fulfill consumers' demands. The gadget accommodates a conveying unit, illumination, cap- Turing unit, and sorting unit. Physical and mechanical capabilities had been extracted from the samples pro- vided, and the detection set of rules become designed accordingly. An index primarily based totally on coloration capabilities become described to locate Date samples. Date result had been consumed a conveyor belt in a row. When they had been in the center of the camera's discipline of view, an image become taken, the photo become processed immediately, and the adulthood degree of the Date become determined. When the Date surpassed the sensor, located on the stop of the conveyor belt, a sign became dispatched to the interface circuit and the precise actuator. Pushed via way of means of a steeper motor, become actuated, main the Date in the direction of the precise port. For validation of proposed gadget performance, whole samples had been once more taken care of via way of means of professionals visually. The detection price of the gadget for Tamar and Khalal became satisfactory. Although the detection price has become inadequate for the Rotab degree, there has been not a sizable distinction between gadget accuracy and that received via way of means of the professionals. The velocity of the photo processing gadget becomes 0.34 s.

Sandeep Badawi et al [6]: Design and Fabrication of Automated Sorting System A sort of gadget used to switch fabric continuously is a belt conveyor. The belt capabilities are due to frictional force. The mining, metallurgical, and coal industries appoint the belt conveyor appreciably because of its trustworthy construction, ease of maintenance, excessive switch capacity, and lengthy switch distance. The important purpose of this mission is to broaden a unique shape of set of rules to achieve a singular degree of approachability in business automation. Without a human, those machines can carry out diverse responsibilities at diverse locations. In our mission, we created a device for robotically rejecting faulty gadgets as they skip through the conveyor device.

A. Chavan and M. N. Kakatkar [7]: Automatic Fruit Sorting and Quality Analyzer supplied look at the fruit sorting machine offers us numerous facts like shape, defect, color, length etc. In gift

days, the grading and type is completed primarily based totally on thorough enjoy and observations i.e. manually. The guide approach is costly, slow, and lacks objectivity and reliability required in numerous aggressive industries. In this project, a machine is designed for sorting and analyzing the pleasant of fruit and it's far applied thru MATLAB. External inspection of the fruit is accomplished through picture processing. The machine makes use of picture processing strategies and embedded machine to examine the pleasant and type the fruits.

Md. Arman Reza Joy et al [8]: Design and Development of Product Sorter Using TSC3200 Colour Sensor paper offered Machines can carry out repetitive duties higher than humans. Worker fatigue on meeting strains can bring about decreased performance, and purpose demanding situations in retaining product quality. A worker who has been acting on an inspection project time and again may also sooner or later fail to apprehend the shade of product. Automating most of the duties withinside the industries may also assist in enhancing the performance of producing machine. The cause of this version is to layout and put into effect a machine which routinely separates merchandise primarily based totally on their shade. This system includes 3 parts: Arduino uno, shade sensor, and servo motor. The output and entrance of sensor and servo motor became interfaced the use of Arduino uno. To lessen human efforts on mechanical maneuvering, one-of-a-kind varieties of sorting machines are being developed. These machines are too steeply priced because of the complexity withinside the fabrication process. A not unusual place requirement withinside the subject of shade sorting is that of shade sensing and identification.

3. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Progression of sensors

The diagram above illustrates the main process controlled by the Arduino controller. Arduino is a straightforward microcontroller board used for developing and uploading software. The Arduino program processes inputs from various modules and sends corresponding signals. The IR sensor detects the flow of objects and transmits this information to the Arduino. The color sensor and MQ gas sensor assess the ripeness and color of the objects. Based on this feedback, the Arduino sends signals to the stepper motor to perform sorting tasks. If the system detects damage, the stepper motor rotates to direct the object to a damage bin. For undamaged items, the system proceeds to size sorting, where objects are sorted and placed into appropriate bins based on their size. The proposed project involves an object sorting system using the following components:

- Arduino Mega Microcontroller
- IR Sensor
- TCS3200 Colour Sensor
- Mq Sensor
- Servo Motor
- 4X4 Matrix Membrane Keypad

Fig 2: - Circuit Diagram

Components Description

Arduino Mega Microcontroller

Fig 3: - Arduino Board

Arduino is a platform for physical computing that is open source that includes a development environment for computer programming along with a simple microprocessor board. It transfers codes from sensor modules, Arduino Mega Microcontroller selected for the project.

IR Sensor

Fig 4: - IR sensor

In addition to detecting motion, an infrared sensor may measure an object's heat. Typically, all items emit some kind of thermal radiation in the infrared range. Although these radiations are undetectable to the human eye, they can be detected by an infrared sensor.

TCS3200 Color Sensor

Fig 5: - Color Sensor

The TCS3200 programmable colour light-to-frequency converters that combine configurable silicon photodiodes and a current-to-frequency converter on a single solid CMOS coordinates circuit. In the TCS3200, the light-to-frequency converter peruses an 8 x 8 cluster of photodiodes. Sixteen photodiodes have blue channels, 16 photodiodes have green channels, 16 photodiodes have ruddy channels, and 16 photodiodes are clear with no channels. All photodiodes of the same colour are associated in parallel. Pins S2 and S3 are utilized to select which bunch of photodiodes (ruddy, green, blue, clear) are dynamic. Photodiodes are 110 μm x 110 μm in measure and are on 134- μm centres.

Mq Sensor

Fig 6: - Mitten gas Sensor

The MQ-2 type smoke sensor is made of a tin dioxide semiconductor gas sensing material. When it works at a temperature of 200 to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the tin dioxide adsorbs the oxygen in the air, which

reduces the density of electrons on the semiconductor and thus increasing the resistance.

Servo Motor

Fig 7: - Servo Motor

A servo motor is a rotary actuator control of angular position. It consists of a motor coupled to a sensor for position feedback. It also requires a servo drive to complete the system. The drive uses the feedback sensor to precisely control the rotary position of the motor.

- Torque: 2.0kg/cm (4.8V), 2.2kg/cm(6V)
- Speed: 0.09s/60° (4.8V), 0.08s/60°(6V)
- Rotate angle: 180°

4. OBJECTIVES

- The project's objective is to sort components based on color and damage.
- Sorting will be performed according to physical attributes such as shape (e.g., circular).
- The model will be constructed as a straightforward digital device, utilizing a microcontroller for processing, servo motors for movement, a color sensor for color recognition, and an MQ gas sensor for detecting ripeness.

CAD MODEL

Fig 8: - Design Model

Sorting Platform: Design a sturdy platform where the fruits/vegetables will be placed for sorting. This platform should be designed to accommodate the weight and size of various fruits/vegetables.

Metal Structures: Create four square box-like metal structures positioned strategically on the sorting platform.

Spoiled Fruits/Vegetable Box: One box is designated specifically for spoiled fruits/vegetables. This box should be easily accessible for disposal or further processing.

Good Fruits/Vegetable Boxes: The remaining three boxes are for good fruits/vegetables. These boxes are differentiated based on their size to accommodate different types of fruits/vegetables.

Small Box: Designed for smaller fruits/vegetables.

Medium Box: Designed for medium-sized fruits/vegetables.

Large Box: Designed for larger fruits/vegetables.

Servo Motor Mount: Design a mounting bracket or platform to securely mount the MG996R servo motor above the sorting platform. This platform should allow the servo motor to move freely and actuate the sorting mechanism.

Enclosure Design: Design an enclosure to protect the electronic components, servo motor, and sorting boxes from environmental factors such as dust, moisture, and physical damage. The enclosure should have openings or access points for loading fruits/vegetables onto the sorting platform and for accessing the sorting boxes for removal.

Main Frame

Fig 9: - Fabrication Model

5.CONCLUSION

The machine is designed to sort a variety of fruits and vegetables of different sizes. It has been tested with produce such as tomatoes, lemons, and guavas. The sorting sequence of the machine was developed to handle various physical and mechanical properties of the sorted items. The proposed technique effectively classifies and grades fruits and vegetables, with promising results for the three tested fruits of the same size. This system is well-suited for applications in agricultural produce marketing and similar fields.

6. REFERENCES

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